

THE USE OF INTELLIGENCE-MAPS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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The innovative direction of the new state educational standards is determined by their purposeful, multifunctional, structural and meaningful elements. New educational standards not only correct the content of education and the proposed educational results, but also provide guarantees for achieving these indicators in the conditions of the existing information and educational environment. In this regard, the implementation of new standards will be possible only with an innovative approach to its implementation, and its prerequisite will be the use of new pedagogical information technologies aimed only at achieving these goals.

The peculiarities of physics are that it studies the simplest, but at the same time General Laws of the material world, in contrast to the sciences of the natural cycle as a fundamental science. Another distinguishing feature is the connection between physics and mathematics, since almost the entire theory of physics is explained using mathematical expressions. And most importantly, all physics is built on experiments based on constant measurements, the need for which is associated with the comparison of the studied phenomena with special standards, which requires special skills, and often equipment [4].

Intelligence-maps are essentially considered in aspects of the formation of creative thinking of students, their personal competencies and creative identity. The use of intelligence-maps to activate the thought process is detailed in the works of Tony Buchanan, Horst Müller [1].

An example of the use of intelligence-maps in the educational process is the preparation of classes on their basis. The stages of application of technology based on the creation of intelligence-maps can be seen on the example of an integrated training lesson [3].

Activation. At this stage, the "interconnection" method is used. Students are shown from 4 to 8 pictures, in which the topic of the lesson, the purpose of the lesson, the holistic topic are encrypted. They need to solve a puzzle that, without the help of others, explains the general idea and topic of the lesson. To reflect on "interdependence", questions should help to activate knowledge. For example,

Movement of a body shot at an angle relative to the horizontal and horizontal.

Incubation. At this stage, the integration of scientific knowledge and real experiences is carried out. This is demonstrated with the help of intelligence-maps, previously prepared for students, which shows the regularity of the application of technology on the basis of the interaction of physics with various areas of human and scientific activity. Incubation is designed to concentrate the participation of students in the study of the material, increase their interest, show the need or benefit of studying the material. From this stage, the effectiveness of students' assimilation of educational material depends in many ways. The teacher prepares students to receive the final product - intelligence-maps, which reflect the constructive and creative foundations of the lesson. For example,

Djoul-Lents law.

Understand. This stage is aimed at organizing the assimilation of new material. One of the main methods of this stage is the demonstration method. As a result, knowledge is enriched by their formative-discursive integrity and positive coloring of the lesson. In addition, the stage includes a series of experiments that help to acquire new knowledge and establish new connections between the objects being integrated.

At this time, the participation of all analyzers (visual, auditory, etc.) occurs in the minds of students, guaranteeing the creation of conditional connections, ensuring the development of speech formation, the ability to compare, generalize and form conclusions.

The discussion of the information base, which is taken as the basis for creating an intelligence-map, continues (for clarity, it is also presented in the form of a "word cloud").

Aprobation. Students complete their intellect-maps based on group work using previously obtained materials, at which time students demonstrate the process of individual method of perception, processing and presentation of information. At the junction of the two areas of knowledge, which are the basis for integrated education, the issue of activating creative thinking is resolved. The student's ability to perceive this or that subject, phenomenon, law, the universe as part of

a holistic whole in cognition is improved. This stage of the lesson provides for the contribution of each participant to work in the group, helps to unite and achieve synergy in the group.

Reflection. The presentation of mental maps of students, their design, what information is encrypted, is discussed with an explanation of the reasons for choosing this information. If necessary, a gentle correction of students' mistakes is carried out. The teacher also reveals his intellect-map for students, the cards of students and the teacher are compared. The teacher can objectively determine to what extent the information is absorbed and processed by students. During the training session, it is determined how correctly the relationship between the studied phenomena and objects is determined.

Analysis. At this stage, self-analysis is carried out, as a result of which each student, relying on the criteria for assessing intelligence-Maps, makes a verdict on the level of achievement achieved, its expected result. For each student, the thinking process is individual, and this is "poured" on paper [2].

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